

Synthesis of square-planar palladium(II) and platinum(II) complexes with *N*-alkylphenothiazines

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Six square-planar complexes with general formula $MLCl_2$ [$M = Pd^{II}$ or Pt^{II} and $L =$ methoxypropazine (MP), prochlorperazine (PCP) or butaperazine (BP)] have been synthesised in ethanol medium. *N*-Alkylphenothiazines act as bidentate ligands, the heterocyclic sulfur and tertiary nitrogen of the chain being the sites of coordination.

N-Alkylphenothiazines (NAP) possess anticholinergic, antihistamine and antiemetic activities^{1,2}. In continuation of our work³, we now report the synthesis of palladium(II) and platinum(II) complexes with *N*-alkylphenothiazines.

	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃
Methoxypropazine maleate (MPM)	$-(CH_2)_3N(CH_3)_2$	$-OCH_3$	$C_4H_4O_4$
10-[3-(Dimethylamino)propyl]-2-methoxyphenothiazine maleate	$-(CH_2)_3N(CH_3)_2$	$-Cl$	$2 C_4H_4O_4$
Prochlorperazine dimaleate (PCPD)	$-(CH_2)_3N(CH_3)_2$	$-Cl$	$2 C_4H_4O_4$
2-Chloro-10-[3-(4-methyl-1-piperazyl)propyl]phenothiazine dimaleate	$-(CH_2)_3N(CH_3)_2$	$-CO(CH_2)_2CH_3$	$2 C_4H_4O_4$
Butaperazine dimaleate (BPD)	$-(CH_2)_3N(CH_3)_2$	$-CO(CH_2)_2CH_3$	$2 C_4H_4O_4$
1-[10-[3-(4-Methyl-1-piperazyl)propyl]phenothiazine-2-yl]-1-butanone dimaleate	$-(CH_2)_3N(CH_3)_2$	$-CO(CH_2)_2CH_3$	$2 C_4H_4O_4$

Results and Discussion

The interaction of palladium(II) chloride or chloroplatinic acid with *N*-alkylphenothiazines in ethanol medium yields palladium(II) or platinum(II) phenothiazine complexes. The maleate and dimaleate ions of the ligand pass into solvent ethanol during the reaction and do not participate in coordination with metal ions. Platinum(IV) in chloroplatinic acid is believed to be reduced to platinum(II) by *N*-alkylphenothiazines which are good reducing agents.

The analytical data of the complexes suggest a general formula $MLCl_2$ (where $M = Pd^{II}$ or Pt^{II} and $L =$ methoxypropazine, prochlorperazine or butaperazine). The complexes are non-hygroscopic and stable at room temperature. They are soluble in DMF and DMSO, slightly

soluble in acetonitrile and chloroform and insoluble in water and other common organic solvents. They do not possess sharp melting points. The molar conductances in DMF are in the range of 38–42 for Pd–NAP complexes and 35–40 $\Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$ range for Pt–NAP complexes in $10^{-3} M$ concentration, indicating the non-electrolyte nature of the complexes. This is consistent with the stoichiometry assumed for the complexes on the basis of the analytical data. All the complexes are diamagnetic as expected for planar coordination around Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} ions in complexes.

Electronic spectra : The intense (red/violet) of the compounds indicate that phenothiazines have high ligand field strength in forming the complexes in which the *d-d* transitions are largely obscured by the more intense charge-transfer bands. A broad band observed at 390–430 nm may be attributed to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$ transition. Weak bands at 320–340 nm in the ligand spectra, probably due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions, are replaced by bands of varying intensity in the spectra of the Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes.

Infrared spectra : It has been reported¹ that the ions R_3N^+H combine with Cl^- ion present in the molecules of *N*-alkylphenothiazines giving a broad IR band at 2500–2300 cm^{-1} . A broad band at 2600–2350 cm^{-1} observed in the IR spectra of the free ligands corresponds to the $-(CH_2)_3N^+H-(CH_3)_2$ in MPM and $-(CH_2)_3HN^+(CH_3)_2$ in PCPD and BPD combined with X^- anion ($X^- =$ maleate or dimaleate). In the spectra of the corresponding Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes, this band is absent showing that the tertiary nitrogen atom of the chain is a site of coordination. The far-IR bands of

the complexes exhibit new bands at 490–480 (Pd–N)⁴ and 330–320 cm⁻¹ (Pt–N)⁵

In aromatic derivatives the ν_{CSC} generally appears as a band of weak or moderate intensity 702–673 cm⁻¹ region⁶. However some difficulty is experienced in recognizing this band in *N*-alkylphenothiazines due to the presence of the intense CH out-of plane deformation band in this region⁷. In all the Pd^{II} and Pt^{II} complexes ν_{CSC} suffers a significant positive shift by 40–30 cm⁻¹. This is attributed to coordination from sulfur atom. New bands appeared at 345–335 cm⁻¹ (Pd–S) for the Pd^{II} complexes and at 330–320 cm⁻¹ (Pt–S) for the Pt complexes⁸. The Pd–Cl and Pt–Cl stretching vibrations for PdLCl₂ and PtLCl₂ are found in the expected range at 302–298 and 345–340 cm⁻¹, respectively for terminal M–Cl bonds⁹ with *cis*-configuration.

Proton NMR spectra In the spectra of prochlorperazine dimaleate and its Pd^{II} complex, the N–CH₃ protons are the highly shielded ones followed by the methylene protons of the alkyl side-chain (N–CH₂). The methylene protons of the piperazine ring and that of the alkyl side-chain absorb at approximately the same field and hence a triplet is obtained in the spectra of PCPD and its complex. A broad hump at δ 9.3 seen in the spectrum of the PCPD assignable to the proton of the COOH group in the maleic acid molecule, disappeared in the spectrum of the corresponding Pd^{II} complex, showing that only the base prochlorperazine is coordinated to the metal. A multiplet appearing at δ 7.0–8.0 in the spectrum of PCPD and its Pd^{II} complex is assignable to the CH protons of the benzene rings.

The absorption peaks associated with the groups attached to nitrogen observed in the spectrum of the ligand are found to be shifted downfield in the spectrum of the corresponding Pd^{II} complex, probably due to the coordinating effect of the nitrogen atom which results in the deshielding of the protons attached to it. Thus ¹H NMR studies confirmed the participation of tertiary nitrogen atom of the alkyl side-chain of NAP in coordination. The ¹H NMR spectrum of Pt–PCP complex resembles closely that of Pd–PCP complex.

Experimental

Palladium chloride and chloroplatinic acid (Arora Matthey Ltd, India), methoxypropazine maleate and prochlorperazine dimaleate (Rhone Poulenc) and butaperazine dimaleate (Bayer) were used. Ethanol, ether, DMF and

DMSO were of AnalaR grade.

Preparation of complexes An ethanolic solution of *N*-alkylphenothiazine (3.4 mmol) was added slowly to an ethanolic solution of palladium(II) chloride (2.8 mmol) with constant stirring. The complexes formed were set aside for 1 h, then washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried under reduced pressure over fused CaCl₂. Pd(MP)Cl₂, red, Pd(PCP)Cl₂, red, Pd(BP)Cl₂, red. The complexes of platinum were prepared similarly by adding ethanolic solutions of *N*-alkylphenothiazines (1.6 mmol) to chloroplatinic acid (1.2 mmol). Pt(MP)Cl₂, red, Pt(PCP) violet, Pt(BP)Cl₂, yellow. All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and Cl analyses.

C, H and N were determined on a Carlo Erba 1106 analyser. Molar conductance was measured in 10⁻³ M DMF solutions using an Elico CM 82T conductivity bridge. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu FTIR 470 spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra (DMSO-*d*₆) on a Hitachi R-600 spectrophotometer with respect to TMS and electronic spectra (DMF) on a JASCO UVIDEK 610 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility was determined by Gouy method at room temperature using Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as calibrant.

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